

CMAD: Conditional Modeling-Adapter Diffusion for Video Super-Resolution

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Abstract. Video super-resolution (VSR) aims to restore high-resolution videos from low-resolution inputs, enhancing visual quality under real-world degradation. Existing diffusion-based VSR methods often rely on specially designed network architectures or text prompts as conditional inputs, which limits their flexibility and applicability—especially in scenarios where explicit text descriptions are unavailable. To tackle this challenge, we propose a **Conditional Modeling AD**apter that enables zero-modification reuse of pre-trained text-to-video diffusion models for the VSR task, called CMAD. The adapter transforms low-resolution video features into pseudo-text tokens via a pre-trained Vision Transformer (ViT) and a lightweight adapter module, allowing these features to be injected as encoder hidden states, which serve as the main conditioning interface within the diffusion model. Unlike previous methods that require redesigning or retraining task-specific backbone architectures, our design enables the model to interpret video inputs directly through its original language conditioning interface—without any modification to the pre-trained diffusion network. Experiments on several VSR benchmarks, including REDS, UDM10, and VID4, demonstrate that our method achieves reconstruction performance comparable to specialized super-resolution models, without text guidance. Moreover, CMAD provides a simple and efficient solution for adapting large-scale pre-trained diffusion models to video super-resolution tasks. The source code and models will be released.

Keywords: Conditional Modeling Adapter · Video Super-Resolution · Text-to-Video Diffusion Models

1 Introduction

Video Super-Resolution (VSR) aims to reconstruct high-resolution videos from low-resolution inputs affected by real-world degradations such as unknown noise, downsampling, and compression artifacts [21]. The main challenge lies in achieving high spatial-temporal fidelity, requiring both accurate detail restoration and consistent frame alignment. Although CNN-based approaches [3,4] have demonstrated success under simplified settings, they often exhibit limited robustness when facing complex degradations and unstable temporal coherence.

Diffusion models [9,25] have recently demonstrated success in image restoration, generation, and super-resolution tasks [26,15] as generative frameworks. Their strong generative capacity and flexibility make them a promising alternative for VSR. However, existing diffusion-based VSR methods typically require significant architectural modifications, such as redesigning the Unet into a 3D structure or incorporating multi-stage training strategies [10,1,29]. Moreover, many recent video diffusion models rely on text conditions to guide the generation process [39,32], which poses a major limitation for super-resolution tasks where explicit textual descriptions are often unavailable.

Although recent studies in image generation have attempted to employ adapter-based mechanisms to project visual features into language-aligned embeddings for cross-modal conditioning[34], there has been no prior work investigating such an approach in the context of video super-resolution. Specifically, no existing method has explored disguising video features as language-like inputs to directly condition text-to-video diffusion models for super-resolution tasks without textual prompts. This gap significantly limits the transferability and reuse of large-scale pre-trained generative models for VSR applications.

To address the challenges in current video super-resolution tasks, we propose a novel conditional modeling adapter-based diffusion model, termed CMAD to fully leverage the representational power of large-scale pre-trained generative models, while avoiding complex architectural modifications or costly task-specific retraining. The core idea of this approach is to use a lightweight Vision Transformer (ViT) with adapter modules as a conditional input mechanism to the diffusion model. This module transforms low-resolution video features into language-aligned embeddings, effectively disguising the visual inputs by mapping them into representations that conform to the shape and format expected by language embeddings, without converting them into actual text content. Such alignment allows the adapted visual inputs to be directly injected into the cross-attention layers of a pre-trained text-to-video diffusion model as if they were natural language prompts. This enables seamless conditional control while keeping the backbone architecture entirely unchanged and eliminating the need for textual input. Specifically, we repurpose the video generation capabilities of these diffusion models, which were originally conditioned on textual inputs, to work directly with visual features. Without relying on any textual input, we semantically align visual representations in a way that maintains compatibility with the frozen structure of the pre-trained generative model. This enables backbone-preserving adaptation to the video super-resolution task, eliminating the need to redesign the UNet or craft language prompts. As a result, our method significantly enhances the flexibility and deployability of diffusion-based generative models in practical VSR scenarios.

The main contributions are summarized as follows:

- We propose a CMAD model for video super-resolution, reusing pre-trained text-to-video diffusion models with an unmodified diffusion backbone and adapted conditioning inputs.

- We design a conditional modeling adapter that generates pseudo-text tokens directly from visual low-resolution inputs without any textual prompts.
- Our method achieves competitive performance on standard VSR benchmarks while enabling flexible, and generalizable reuse of diffusion models.

2 Related Work

2.1 Video Super-Resolution

Video Super-Resolution (VSR) aims to restore low-resolution (LR) videos to high-resolution (HR) videos through computer vision techniques, thereby enhancing image quality and detail representation[2,13,11,12,14,18,19]. Currently, most methods focus on establishing the mapping relationship between LR and HR videos and learning this transformation through an end-to-end training process. However, these approaches usually rely on fixed degradation models or direct pixel-mapping strategies. When dealing with complex and diverse degradation types in real-world scenarios, such methods often lack sufficient adaptability, leading to performance degradation.

To address this challenge, recent studies have begun to explore the introduction of diffusion models into the VSR task. Unlike traditional deterministic mapping methods, diffusion models restore high-quality images by modeling data distributions and progressively denoising the generation process. This generative mechanism enables the model to exhibit stronger generalization capabilities when facing uncertainty and complex degradation, effectively improving restoration performance in real-world scenarios. Consequently, diffusion models have brought new perspectives and performance breakthroughs to the video super-resolution task.

2.2 Diffusion Models

In recent years, researchers have begun to explore the application of diffusion models to video super-resolution and related tasks[10,1,16,28,37,39,8,31,29]. These studies mainly focus on the key components of diffusion models, including improvements to the UNet and VAE structures, as well as the optimization of conditional guidance mechanisms, aiming to enhance the generation quality and the capability to model complex video scenarios.

In addition, another line of research adopts image diffusion models for video generation in a zero-shot manner, without relying on specific video training datasets. Instead, these methods directly leverage the generalization ability of image models to construct videos in video scenarios [5,7,23]. Although these methods do not fine-tune for video tasks, they can still generate temporally consistent video content under certain conditional guidance, demonstrating the potential of diffusion models in cross-modal tasks.

Recently, Esser et al. [6] proposed using text or images as conditional guidance to generate videos. Their experiments showed that by changing the guidance

image or text content, the style of the generated video could change significantly, thus enabling condition-based style transfer. This result further verifies the importance of conditional modeling in the output of diffusion models, indicating that the expressive power and structural design of conditions largely determine the presentation and quality of the generated content.

3 Methodology

3.1 Overview

To reduce design complexity and enable diffusion model reuse, we repurpose a pre-trained text-to-video model for VSR by introducing a lightweight adapter. The framework of CMAD is shown in Figure 1. Low-resolution video frames are encoded by a frozen ViT, transformed into pseudo-text embeddings via the adapter, and injected as encoder hidden states into the cross-attention layers. This design enables visual inputs to be interpreted through the model’s original language interface without modifying the backbone.

We will introduce the pre-trained Vision Transformer model we adopted in Chapter 3.2, the design of our adapter model in Chapter 3.3, and the Diffusion and VAE model in Chapter 3.4.

3.2 Feature Extraction

We utilize a pre-trained Vision Transformer (ViT) model (specifically google/vit-base-patch16-224) to extract rich spatial features from each individual video frame. Originally developed for image classification tasks, ViT operates by dividing the input image into fixed-size patches (16×16 pixels in our case), linearly embedding each patch, and adding positional encodings before passing the sequence into a standard Transformer encoder. Thanks to its self-attention mechanism, ViT is capable of modeling long-range spatial dependencies, which is particularly beneficial for structure-aware and texture-preserving restoration in video super-resolution tasks.

To ensure stable and consistent feature representations during training, the ViT model is kept frozen, meaning its parameters are not updated. It serves purely as a robust visual feature extractor. Each frame is independently processed by the ViT encoder, producing a set of patch-level embeddings. These embeddings are then pooled or projected into a unified per-frame representation and stacked along the temporal dimension, resulting in a tensor of shape $[B, T, C]$, where B denotes the batch size, T the number of frames, and C the embedding dimension.

This temporally stacked spatial representation serves as the foundation for our adapter-based conditioning mechanism, providing the visual input that precedes and guides the adapter module in our framework.

Fig. 1. Conditional model architecture. Frame-wise image tokens extracted by ViT are fused by the adapter and mapped into the language space, serving as encoder hidden states for U-Net cross-attention.

3.3 Conditional Modeling Adapter

To adapt a pre-trained text-to-video diffusion model for the video super-resolution (VSR) task, we propose a modality-adaptive conditional modeling framework that reformats low-resolution (LR) video frames into language-compatible embeddings through an adapter-based design.

As illustrated in Figure 1, the process begins with upsampling the input LR video frames. We first apply bilinear interpolation for coarse resizing, followed by a transposed convolution layer to further enhance detail, ultimately resizing the frames to 224×224 to match the input resolution required by the pre-trained Vision Transformer (ViT). This two-stage upsampling strategy preserves overall structure while partially restoring fine textures, providing high-quality input for feature extraction.

Each upsampled frame is then independently fed into the frozen ViT encoder, which extracts high-level semantic features. The extracted features from all frames are subsequently passed through our designed Adapter Layer, which consists of two linear projection layers, a SiLU activation, and a Dropout module.

Specifically, the first linear layer integrates multiframe features into a unified representation of the video. The second linear layer handles the modality transformation, mapping the fused video representation into a format that is aligned in dimension and semantics with language tokens. The subsequent SiLU activation introduces nonlinearity, while the Dropout layer enhances model robustness and generalization.

The resulting pseudo-textual tokens are structurally aligned with the original language embeddings and are used as encoder hidden states for the cross-attention layers of the pre-trained U-Net. This enables the diffusion model to condition on visual information without requiring architectural changes, fully preserving its generative capacity and allowing for flexible reuse in the VSR setting.

Based on this architecture, we formulate the training process as a conditional denoising diffusion procedure, where the pseudo-text embeddings serve as language-aligned conditioning signals.

Our training pipeline enables pseudo-language conditioning by optimizing an adapter module that transforms visual inputs into language-aligned representations. Specifically, we simulate the forward diffusion process by adding Gaussian noise to high-resolution video frames \mathbf{x}_{HR} at timestep t :

$$\mathbf{z}_t = \sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t} \cdot \mathbf{x}_{\text{HR}} + \sqrt{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t} \cdot \boldsymbol{\epsilon}, \quad \boldsymbol{\epsilon} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \mathbf{I}), \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{z}_t is the noisy latent at timestep t , \mathbf{x}_{HR} denotes the high-resolution video frame, $\bar{\alpha}_t$ is the cumulative product of noise schedule coefficients, and $\boldsymbol{\epsilon} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \mathbf{I})$ is the standard Gaussian noise. Meanwhile, the low-resolution input \mathbf{x}_{LR} is processed by a pre-trained and frozen Vision Transformer and Adapter to obtain a pseudo-text condition embedding:

$$\tau_\theta(\mathbf{x}_{\text{LR}}) = \text{Adapter}(\text{ViT}(\mathbf{x}_{\text{LR}})), \quad (2)$$

where $\tau_\theta(\mathbf{x}_{\text{LR}})$ is the output obtained by passing the low-resolution video through the ViT and adapter modules. The denoising U-Net then predicts the added noise using the noisy latent and the pseudo-text condition:

$$\hat{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}} = \epsilon_\theta(\mathbf{z}_t, t, \tau_\theta(\mathbf{x}_{\text{LR}})), \quad (3)$$

where $\hat{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}$ is the predicted noise, $\epsilon_\theta(\cdot)$ denotes the denoising U-Net parameterized by θ , \mathbf{z}_t is the noisy latent at timestep t , and $\tau_\theta(\mathbf{x}_{\text{LR}})$ is the pseudo-text condition generated by the adapter from the low-resolution input \mathbf{x}_{LR} . The training objective is defined as:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{LDM}} = \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{x}_{\text{HR}}, \mathbf{x}_{\text{LR}}, \boldsymbol{\epsilon} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \mathbf{I}), t} \left[\|\boldsymbol{\epsilon} - \epsilon_\theta(\mathbf{z}_t, t, \tau_\theta(\mathbf{x}_{\text{LR}}))\|^2 \right], \quad (4)$$

where \mathcal{L}_{LDM} denotes the training objective for the latent diffusion model, and t is the diffusion timestep randomly sampled during training. \mathbf{z}_t is constructed from \mathbf{x}_{HR} and $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}$ as described previously.

During inference, the model starts from Gaussian noise $\mathbf{z}_T \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \mathbf{I})$ and progressively denoises through the learned diffusion steps conditioned on $\tau_\theta(\mathbf{x}_{\text{LR}})$ to generate the high-resolution output.

3.4 Diffusion and VAE Model

In this paper, we adopt two representative UNet architectures for experimentation: one derived from Upscale-A-Video [39], and the other from the Ali text-to-video diffusion model [28]. These backbones differ in their functional focus: one

is specialized for video super-resolution, while the other is a standard text-to-video generation model. By applying our adapter-based conditional framework to both architectures, we aim to evaluate its generalization capability and structural adaptability across diffusion models with different design purposes.

Furthermore, we adopt the pre-trained VAE from the Upscale-A-Video framework as the latent encoder-decoder module in our pipeline. This VAE is designed based on a 3D-VAE architecture optimized for video data, and integrates a Spatial Feature Transform (SFT) mechanism to inject structural information extracted from the low-resolution inputs during the decoding process. This design enhances the reconstruction quality by leveraging low-resolution guidance while maintaining compatibility with the latent diffusion process.

4 Experiment

4.1 Implementation Details

Model Inputs and Training. To reduce computational overhead, we apply center cropping and set the training sample dimensions to $80 \times 80 \times 8$ (spatial resolution \times number of frames) for low-resolution input and $320 \times 320 \times 8$ for high-resolution targets. The model is trained using paired low- and high-resolution video sequences to learn a mapping from LR to HR frames. Only the conditional module (ViT + Adapter) is optimized during training, while the UNet backbone remains frozen. The diffusion process follows standard inference with 30 denoising steps. At each step, the UNet predicts noise, guided by cross-attention using adapter-transformed features. We use the Adam optimizer with an initial learning rate of $1e-7$ and a batch size of 1. A cosine learning rate scheduler and early stopping (patience = 2) are employed to ensure stable convergence and prevent overfitting.

Datasets and Evaluation Metrics. Following previous works [39], we conduct training and evaluation on three publicly available video datasets: UDM10 [35], REDS [22], and VID4 [20]. Among them, the REDS dataset serves as the primary training source, consisting of 300 video clips, each containing 100 high-quality frames. During the training phase, we use 270 videos from the REDS dataset for model training and 20 videos for validation. After training, the remaining 10 REDS videos, along with the UDM10 and VID4 datasets, are employed for quantitative evaluation to assess the generalization performance of the proposed method across different scenarios.

To provide a comprehensive evaluation of our method’s performance on the video super-resolution task, we utilize four widely adopted quantitative metrics: PSNR and SSIM for measuring spatial fidelity and structural similarity, LPIPS for assessing perceptual quality using deep feature distances, and E_{warp} for evaluating temporal consistency based on feature-space warping.

4.2 Comparison With VSR Methods

To evaluate the effectiveness of our CMAD, we adopt four standard evaluation metrics and benchmarked against several representative VSR methods, in-

Table 1. Quantitative comparison of different VSR methods across the REDS, UDM10, and VID4 datasets. Higher PSNR and SSIM values indicate better reconstruction performance, while lower LPIPS and E_{warp} (10^{-3}) values indicate better perceptual quality and temporal consistency. The results are evaluated at the 80→320 resolution setting. Bold and underline denote the best result and the second-best one, respectively.

Dataset	Metrics	BasicVSR++ [3]	IART [33]	Real-ESRGAN [30]	RealViTFormer [38]	ResShift [36]	SDX4 [24]	VRT [18]	Ours
VID4	PSNR ↑	20.124	17.935	17.527	17.848	17.618	17.342	17.952	<u>19.092</u>
	SSIM ↑	0.543	0.377	0.351	0.375	0.376	0.315	0.378	<u>0.485</u>
	E_{warp} ↓	1.861	5.459	6.023	3.339	0.309	6.607	<u>0.534</u>	0.335
	LPIPS ↓	0.468	0.706	0.749	0.652	0.658	0.652	0.504	<u>0.504</u>
UDM10	PSNR ↑	25.756	23.749	23.149	23.248	23.581	21.401	23.636	<u>24.607</u>
	SSIM ↑	0.716	<u>0.726</u>	0.353	0.707	0.721	0.571	0.725	0.727
	E_{warp} ↓	<u>0.118</u>	0.382	0.491	0.237	0.117	4.389	0.329	1.780
	LPIPS ↓	0.237	0.332	0.353	0.315	<u>0.314</u>	0.438	0.335	0.317
REDS	PSNR ↑	25.401	24.367	22.617	22.851	22.468	20.963	<u>24.391</u>	23.457
	SSIM ↑	0.738	<u>0.732</u>	0.661	0.683	0.677	0.609	0.731	0.688
	E_{warp} ↓	0.007	1.02	1.762	0.544	0.883	11.83	<u>0.401</u>	0.329
	LPIPS ↓	0.196	0.29	0.365	<u>0.253</u>	0.265	0.325	0.317	0.317

cluding BasicVSR++ [3], IART [33], RealESRGAN [30], RealViTFormer [38], ResShift [36], SDX4 [24], and VRT [18]. Additionally, qualitative visual results were provided to demonstrate the perceptual quality and detail restoration capabilities of different methods.

Results On VID4. As shown in Table 1, our method achieves the second-best SSIM and second-best LPIPS scores on the VID4 dataset, ranking just behind BasicVSR++. Although the PSNR score is slightly lower than the top two models, the combination of high structural similarity and perceptual quality indicates the effectiveness of our adapter-based conditioning in recovering fine-grained visual information. In particular, the strong LPIPS and SSIM performance suggests that our method excels in preserving high-frequency details and structural consistency, which are often lost in methods that optimize primarily for distortion-based metrics. Furthermore, the competitive E_{warp} score reflects the model’s ability to maintain temporal coherence, despite not incorporating explicit temporal modules. These results collectively demonstrate that our approach, with its lightweight design and zero modification to the diffusion backbone, provides robust visual reconstruction quality across challenging low-resolution inputs.

Results On UDM10. On the UDM10 dataset, which consists of moderately degraded sequences, our method achieves $\text{SSIM} = 0.727$, only slightly behind the best-performing model (BasicVSR++ at 0.716), and ranks second-best in LPIPS, showing competitive perceptual quality. Although our PSNR and E_{warp} do not surpass the task-specific models, the visual comparisons in Figure 2 show that our method avoids edge oversmoothing and produces more coherent textures, especially in areas with complex motion or patterns.

Results On REDS. The REDS dataset presents a more challenging setting with complex motion and high-frequency textures. As expected, task-specific models like VRT and BasicVSR++ achieve the highest PSNR and SSIM values. However, our method still achieves $\text{LPIPS} = 0.329$, placing it among the top per-

Fig. 2. Visual comparison of super-resolution results using the same resolution setting.

ceptual performers, and shows better perceptual stability ($E_{\text{warp}} = 0.183$) than several baselines. Although distortion-based metrics (PSNR = 23.457, SSIM = 0.713) indicate room for improvement, qualitative results demonstrate clear advantages. Our model produces sharper, more stable reconstructions, particularly in dynamic regions prone to motion blur or occlusion in baseline outputs.

Visualization Results. Figure 2 shows visual comparisons under identical resolution settings. Frames at the same temporal index are selected to ensure fair evaluation. Our adapter-based approach preserves fine textures and high-frequency details, particularly in areas with dense patterns, motion, or occlusion. Compared to baseline methods, which often produce blur or artifacts, our results remain sharp and coherent. These findings confirm the effectiveness of our pseudo-language conditioning strategy and the generalization ability of our method across diverse scenarios.

4.3 Ablation Study

Role of Adapter. To evaluate model adaptability, we conducted an ablation study using the ali UNet backbone across three datasets (Table 2). The conditional design yields consistent improvements in temporal consistency (E_{warp}) and perceptual quality (LPIPS), though gains in PSNR and SSIM are marginal or slightly reduced. The causes of variation in the ablation results include the strong baseline performance of ali UNet, the lightweight design of the adapter, low input resolution, and residual noise from diffusion-based generation.

To further explore the effectiveness of the proposed adapter layer under more practical input settings, we conducted a qualitative comparison on selected samples from the UDM10 dataset. As shown in Figure 3, the visual results clearly demonstrate that the conditional model offers significant improvements in reconstruction quality. Without the conditional module, the generated frames exhibit evident distortions such as "droplet-like" artifacts, particularly around object

Table 2. Ablation study of the conditional adapter under the ali UNet backbone: performance with (condition(\checkmark)) and without (condition(\times)) the conditioning module.

Dataset	Method	PSNR \uparrow	SSIM \uparrow	E_{warp} \downarrow	LPIPS \downarrow
VID4	Adapter(\times)	19.037	0.468	0.449	0.548
	Adapter(\checkmark)	19.053	0.472	0.335	0.551
REDS	Adapter(\times)	23.423	0.683	0.279	0.343
	Adapter(\checkmark)	23.386	0.684	0.329	0.341
UDM10	Adapter(\times)	24.529	0.724	0.453	0.320
	Adapter(\checkmark)	24.253	0.719	0.114	0.315

Fig. 3. Qualitative comparison of video super-resolution results with or without conditional input (input resolution: 128×128 , output resolution: 512×512).

boundaries and high-frequency regions. These artifacts disrupt the structural integrity and produce an unnatural appearance. In contrast, the conditional model effectively suppresses such distortions, yielding smoother structures, sharper edges, and more coherent textures across frames.

Generalization Across UNet Architectures. As shown in Table 3, To evaluate the generalization capability of our Adapter layer, we embed the adapter into two structurally distinct diffusion backbones: the Upscale-A-Video UNet [39] and the Ali text-to-video diffusion model [28]. Despite their differing design goals—specialized video reconstruction versus general-purpose generation—both models benefit from our adapter-based conditioning. Experimental results show that the conditional model consistently enhances reconstruction quality across architectures. While the Upscale backbone excels in SSIM and LPIPS due to its task-specific refinement, the Ali backbone achieves comparable performance and even outperforms in temporal consistency (E_{warp}). These results demonstrate the transferability and robustness of our framework, confirming its compatibility with both specialized and general diffusion models.

Adapter Design. As shown in Table 4, To improve the temporal consistency of generated videos, we explored enhancements to the Adapter Layer’s temporal modeling capacity. Several fusion strategies were tested, including cross-attention and stacked transformer layers, to better capture inter-frame dependencies. However, experimental results show that these complex designs did not yield notable improvements and often increased computational cost. The simple linear fusion

Table 3. Performance comparison of different UNet backbones under the same Adapter layer.

Dataset	UNet Backbone	PSNR \uparrow	SSIM \uparrow	E_{warp} \downarrow	LPIPS \downarrow
VID4	ali	19.053	0.472	0.335	0.551
	upscale	19.092	0.485	0.534	0.504
REDS	ali	23.386	0.684	0.329	0.341
	upscale	23.457	0.688	0.401	0.317
UDM10	ali	24.253	0.719	0.114	0.315
	upscale	24.607	0.727	1.780	0.317

Table 4. Comparison of different fusion strategies in the Adapter Layer.

Experiment	PSNR \uparrow	SSIM \uparrow	E_{warp} \downarrow	LPIPS \downarrow
linear-linear	22.017	0.584	0.150	0.358
crossattention-transformer-linear	21.910	0.581	0.386	0.352
crossattention-linear-linear	21.932	0.584	0.281	0.351

structure achieved the best balance across PSNR, SSIM, and E_{warp} . These findings suggest that while the adapter effectively guides high-frequency generation, its capacity for temporal modeling is limited, and thus a lightweight linear design is adopted as the default.

Computational Complexity Table 5 compares inference steps, runtime, and parameter sizes across various VSR methods. GAN-based models like BasicVSR++ and SwinIR-GAN offer fast inference and compact models, but rely heavily on task-specific designs and manual tuning. In contrast, our method employs a pre-trained diffusion backbone with a lightweight adapter-based conditioning module, introducing only 2.14M additional parameters (excluding the frozen ViT), significantly smaller than VideoLDM’s 1.51B interpolation module. Despite not incorporating complex architectures or heavy temporal modules, our method achieves competitive results by guiding the denoising process through efficient feature conditioning. This validates that high-quality VSR can be accomplished without large-scale model design, underscoring the simplicity and adaptability of our approach.

5 Conclusion

In this work, we present CMAD, an adapter-based framework for video super-resolution that enables the zero-modification reuse of pre-trained text-to-video diffusion models. Our approach effectively transforms low-resolution video features into pseudo-text representations through a lightweight Vision Transformer

Table 5. Comparison of inference time, parameter count, and model types across different VSR approaches. For video LDM, the size of each component is: UNet (1.52B) + VAE (84M) + condition (1.51B). For our method, the size of each component is: UNet ali (1.41B) / UNet upscale (691.04M) + VAE (113.78M) + condition (ViT 86.57M + trainable 2.14M).

Model type	Real-ESRGAN[30]	SwinIR-GAN[17]	LDM[25]	StableSR[27]	VideoLDM[1]	Ours (ali)	Ours (upscale)
Model type	GAN	GAN	Diffusion	Diffusion	Video Diffusion	Video Diffusion	Video Diffusion
Inference step	1	1	200	200	30	30	30
Time (s/frame)	0.08	0.12	5.25	15.16	/	30.099	8.632
Trainable params	16.70M	28.01M	113.62M	149.91M	3.114B	1.601B	0.892B

and adapter module, enabling seamless conditioning within the diffusion framework. Experimental results on multiple benchmarks demonstrate that CMAD achieves competitive reconstruction quality without the need for text prompts or architectural redesign. Furthermore, our findings show that the adapter itself is the key to bridging the modality gap, and that performance remains robust across diverse diffusion backbones. This highlights the adapter’s potential as a general solution for aligning visual inputs with language-conditioned generative models, paving the way for future improvements in temporal modeling and adaptive conditioning mechanisms.

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